

[original idea/conjecture]

Diamond Open Access

[waiting peer review]

The interior of a black hole and the void of spacetime

Open Physics Collaboration*†

May 27, 2021

Abstract

This article connects the following concepts: the “interior of a black hole” with the “void of spacetime,” by means of a thought experiment [1].

keywords: hollow black hole, spacetime, void, vacuum, quantum gravity

The most updated version of this white paper is available at

<https://osf.io/awfx8/download>
<https://zenodo.org/record/4824551>

Introduction

1. Lobo [2] presented a thought experiment conjecturing that spacetime tears apart at the singularity of a black hole.
2. Here, I present the logical steps involved in this thought experiment in the light of the *Open Journal of Mathematics and Physics (OJMP)* [3].
3. One can understand the context of this topic by consulting [2] and the references therein.

*All *authors* with their *affiliations* appear at the end of this white paper.

†Corresponding author: mp1obo@uft.edu.br | **Open Physics Collaboration**

Matter stays in the event horizon of the black hole

4. Suppose that spacetime supports only the maximum Planck density.
5. Suppose that spacetime tears apart when matter and energy surpass this maximum limit on density.
6. When a typical star is becoming a black hole, its mass starts to compress towards the singularity.
7. At some point, the singularity will eventually reach the Planck density.
8. After that, more mass will continue to be attracted to the center of the collapsing star, and spacetime will tear apart due to (4) and (5).
9. The mass that previously occupied the singularity will move to the border of the Planck-volume hole formed by the void of spacetime.
10. The hole in the singularity represents a change in the topology of spacetime, and it creates a pull-back force in the same way that a rubber band would do.
11. (10) holds because of the accelerating expansion of the universe.
12. To visualize (10) and (11), keep pulling a rubber band by all sides and make a hole in its center.
13. The process continues so on and so forth until it reaches the equilibrium at the event horizon.
14. Therefore, *all matter stays in the event horizon of the black hole.*

Final Remarks

15. The initial motivation for this claim arose out from the fact that the black hole entropy depends on its area, namely $S = A/4$.

16. Therefore, all microstates are on the surface of the black hole.
17. This agrees with the firewall proposal and with no information being lost in the black hole whatsoever.

Open Invitation

Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [4, 5].

Join the **Open Physics Collaboration**.

Send your contribution to `mplobo@uft.edu.br`.

Open Science

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [6].

How to cite this paper?

<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/awfx8>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4824551>

Acknowledgements

+ **Open Science Framework**

<https://osf.io>

+ **Zenodo**

<https://zenodo.org>

Agreement

18. All authors **agree** with [5].

References

- [1] Lobo, Matheus P. “Universal Scientific Database.” *OSF Preprints*, 27 Apr. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/4whbp>
- [2] Lobo, Matheus P. “A Hole in the Black Hole.” *OSF Preprints*, 18 Apr. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/js7rf>
- [3] Lobo, Matheus P. (Chief Editor). *Open Journal of Mathematics and Physics (OJMP)*. <https://ojmp.wordpress.com>
- [4] Lobo, Matheus P. “Microarticles.” *OSF Preprints*, 28 Oct. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ejrct>
- [5] Lobo, Matheus P. “Simple Guidelines for Authors: Open Journal of Mathematics and Physics.” *OSF Preprints*, 15 Nov. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/fk836>
- [6] Lobo, Matheus P. “Open Journal of Mathematics and Physics (OJMP).” *OSF*, 21 Apr. 2020. <https://osf.io/6hzyp/files>

The Open Physics Collaboration

Matheus Pereira Lobo (lead author, mplobo@uft.edu.br)¹
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4554-1372>

¹Federal University of Tocantins (Brazil)